

Cover

Abstract: IRAISE: BRIDGING THE GAP IN HEALTHCARE INNOVATION ADOPTION THROUGH COLLABORATIVE EDUCATION AND INDUSTRY ENGAGEMENT

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<p>Abstract</p>	<p>Introduction:Healthcare innovation adoption faces significant challenges, with less than 25% of public R&D grants resulting in commercialization and over 50% of public procurements failing to achieve their goals. To address this gap, the iRaise Education Programme was developed as a collaborative initiative between public and private entities to boost innovation adoption in healthcare settings through targeted professional education.</p> <p>Methodology:iRaise implements an 11-week comprehensive training program targeting multidisciplinary teams from healthcare organizations. The program consists of three main components: classroom sessions, mentoring, and industry engagement through the iRaise Innovation Institutional & Industry Alliance (I3A). The curriculum focuses on developing essential skills including problem analysis, project management, teamwork, leadership, and effective communication. Participants work on real unmet healthcare needs, learning to frame problems, define solutions, and select appropriate vehicles for innovation adoption. The program emphasizes a bottom-up approach to identifying needs and involves all stakeholders impacted by potential innovations.</p> <p>Results:The program successfully created a community of communities including course participants, alumni, mentors, lecturers, and professionals from industry, institutional entities, and innovation networks. Through I3A, the initiative facilitated knowledge transfer between healthcare providers and industry partners, enabling better understanding of market facilitators and barriers. The program equipped healthcare professionals with tools to assess innovation adoption opportunities while building trust between industry players and future adopters of their technologies.</p> <p>Conclusions:iRaise demonstrates an effective educational model for accelerating healthcare innovation adoption by combining structured learning with practical application and industry engagement. The program's success in creating innovation evangelists within healthcare organizations suggests its potential as a scalable approach to addressing the persistent challenges in healthcare innovation adoption. The emphasis on multidisciplinary teams and stakeholder involvement appears crucial for ensuring innovations effectively address real unmet needs and achieve successful adoption.</p>

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